

Bioactive exopolysaccharide from *Neopestalotiopsis* sp. strain SKE15: Production, characterization and optimization

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Abstract

Fungal exopolysaccharides are powerful resources of medicinal applications. *Neopestalotiopsis* sp. SKE15 was iso-lated and identified according to phenotypical and genotypical analyses (GenBank Accession No. MG649986). The exopolysaccharide (EPS) was produced by cultivation of mycelia in broth culture and extracted. The production was optimized to 2.02 g/l after selection of agitation, temperature, FeSO₄ and K₂HPO₄ concentrations as the most influencing factors using Plackett-Burman design and then by applying response surface methodology. Analytical Tools showed that the EPS is composed of a polysaccharide (1.5–2.1 × 10⁶ Da) and its probable low molecular weight derivatives, in a wide range of chain lengths, among them an oligosaccharide of about 1970 Da was dominant. GC–MS (Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry) analysis revealed the EPS was mainly constructed from D-glucose, sorbitol and D-galactose. The EPS showed antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6633 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853. DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl) and hydroxyl radical scavenging activity assays showed strong antioxidant activity of the EPS. A challenge with three different cancerous cell lines showed cytotoxic activity of the EPS at final concentration of 100 and 200 µg/ml. Further investigation on medicinal applications of the biopolymer is promising.

Keywords: Fungal biopolymer, Bioactivity, Exopolysaccharide, oligosaccharide, response surface methodology